

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 1, April - 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10592185

CONVERSATION CIRCLE: TAKING CARE OF THOSE WHO CARE FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF “EMPOWERMENT” ATTITUDES

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ABSTRACT

Reflect on the historicity of Disability and the vision of disability in the present day, where disability is no longer considered a disease but a condition. potentialities and the inclusion of People with Disabilities. This article aims to describe the experiences of an institution in Niterói, dedicated to the care of people with intellectual disabilities and multiple disabilities, the Associação de Pais e Amigos do Excepcionais (APAE – NITERÓI), which experiences the transformation, by developing a process of joint reconstruction work, involving the main actors of care in the rehabilitation process, involving the Person with Disability, the family and health professionals, to favor social inclusion. As the main device for building this paradigmatic transformation, the technical team has been producing several Rounds of Conversations, with the different actors in this process to reflect on the theme of capacitism and the obstacles to social inclusion. The Conversation Wheel Project defines its mission, goals and objectives based on welcoming families. Thus, by articulating with the institution's professionals, prevention actions, guidance and establishment of support groups for parents, intending to improve the quality of life of these families. By creating spaces for exchanges between parents, administrators and professionals, sociability and the ability of these groups to participate in the institution are increased, thus expanding everyone's commitment to the full development of the patient, in their particularities and favoring the social inclusion and neutralizing capacitist actions.

Keywords: Capacitance. Deficiency. Conversation Wheel.

INTRODUCTION

Disability is not a disease, it is a condition. It is urgently necessary to change the point of view and understand that places are deficient, ideas are deficient, our ways of teaching and the solutions that society insists on doing even if it knows, does not include all people. A less capable society is one that thinks of all people, including those with disabilities, who are not heroes or victims of their condition, but capable and productive subjects within their potential and equivalence.

For Mello (2014), ableism is the materialization of attitudes permeated by prejudice that categorize subjects according to the adequacy of their bodies to an ideal of beauty and functional capacity. It is a concept present in the social that evaluates people with disabilities as unequal, less able or incapable of managing their own lives, being for the ableists, disability as a diminished state of the human being. It is a form of subliminal prejudice embedded in social symbolic production, showing a universalized construction of oppression on the understanding of disability (DIAS, 2013).

There are indications since prehistoric times that man already lived with disability. Over the century, people with disabilities have been involved in narratives of abandonment, rejection, many different narratives. First, for not having the same rhythm when we were nomadic people, then for not having the perfect, beautiful and strong body as the Greeks conceptualized. At a given moment, people with disabilities are seen as aberrations, "God's punishment" and then labeled as sick and treated as they are until the present day.

In this social historical context and given the complexity that is the process of rehabilitation to inclusion, the present study aims to demonstrate how, by adjusting and innovating different care actions in their work processes, APAE - Niterói, an institution in the city of Niterói that serves People with Intellectual Disabilities and Multiple Disabilities, seeks to transform perspectives and promote reflections, having as a methodology the implementation of the Conversation Circle device, addressing various themes for the promotion of technical intervention actions to help families, expanding attention also to care who takes care of. Believing that by offering this care, a critical

reflection on the situations experienced by families that have a person with a disability at their core is promoted, and that the perception of the dimensions of care is favored, resuming the role of the family, redirecting care and providing tools for the family to build new plans, eliminating the barriers of ability.

Capacitism

Reflecting on the historicity of Disability and the vision of disability in the present day, it is understood that ableism is constituted as a designation, as it designates prejudiced attitudes towards people with disabilities.

According to Guimarães (2013), the designation is considered as the meaning of a name as its relationship with other names and with the world, historically cut by the name. The designation is not something abstract, but linguistic and historical.

According to the above, we can highlight the definition of ableism, present in the Glossary of terms related to accessibility and disability of the Chamber of Deputies:

Capacitism: act of discrimination, prejudice or oppression against a person with a disability. It is an attitudinal barrier. In general, it occurs when someone considers a person incapable, due to differences and bodily impediments. Capacitism is focused on the supposed 'capacities of people without disabilities' as a reference to show the supposed 'limitations of people with disabilities'. In ableism, emphasis is placed on the supposed 'capable people', who make up the majority of the population and are supposedly considered 'normal'.

Starting from the logic of prejudice, we observed that ableism alludes to an unfavorable opinion about the person with a disability, a previous opinion, often based on the imaginary about the person with a disability, in which he is seen as someone without the ability to have autonomy and independence to manage their own lives (MARCHESAN, et al, 2021).

Also according to MARCHESAN, et al, seeing the disabled person in a preconceived and limiting view comes from a socio-historical constitution

of thoughts that underlie a series of prejudices, because it presupposes that these subjects have limitations that disable them in all instances of life, causing their capabilities to be suppressed by a totalizing and excluding discourse.

Historically contextualizing, disability is described in the subjects' bodies and its understanding has gone through various configurations, from religious and supernatural conceptions, through the biomedical model, to the biopsychosocial model, which overlaps in national and international legislation. It started from the integrationist discourse, in the which person with disabilities must adapt to society, to the inclusive discourse, when there is a process of adjustment of both the person with disability and society. According to Aranha (2001), the difference between integration and inclusion lies in the fact that, while the former emphasizes the "readiness" of the subject for life in the community", the later invests in the development of the subject and in the creation of conditions that guarantee the access and participation of people with disabilities in society, through supports, whether physical, psychological, or yet another.

Therefore, social inclusion happens when there is an adjustment process for both the person with a disability and society. Inclusion is an open process, it is something to be built together and that still needs planning, experimentation because its improvement is necessary for future generations. (SPIDER, 2001).

In his studies, Aranha (2001) also mentions that both must act together for inclusion to take place in social practice, as there are interventions both in the subject's development process and in the social readjustment process.

However, in today's society, still a large part of social initiatives are directed to a universal subject, commonly represented by the "standard" and idealized man, and the exclusion, in this way, the denial of all human diversity. Medeiros and Mudado (2010) explain that, by denying the ethical imperatives of responsibility and commitment to human beings, social exclusion is tinged with prejudice by affirming an ideal of a biologically perfect man.

In fact, inclusion requires a long trajectory, with a view to transforming everyone's social practice.

In this study, we describe the experience of an institution in Niterói, dedicated to the care of people with intellectual disabilities and multiple disabilities, the Associação de Pais e Amigos do Excepcional (APAE – Niterói), which experiences this transformation by developing a work process of joint reconstruction, involving the main actors of care in the rehabilitation process, starring the Person with Disabilities, the family and health professionals, to favor social inclusion.

Faced with the complexity of the process from rehabilitation to inclusion, it is necessary to adjust and innovate different care actions, as well as to apply comprehensive care on its various fronts, seeking to unite health, care and education actions, based on the disability care policy. As a result, the institution has been structuring and reorganizing its actions, with the objective of promoting the leading role of people with disabilities, through activities for the development of their potential; of education and information for the development of the subject, with actions aimed at self-defense. And in parallel, the work of assistance to family members, which provide the trust and credibility of People with Disabilities (PwD), respecting their limits and their diversity, in order to minimize the barriers imposed by the ability.

As the main device for the construction of this paradigmatic transformation, the technical team has been producing several Conversation Rounds, with the different actors of this process to reflect on the theme of capacitism and the obstacles to social inclusion.

In this study, we will pay attention to Conversation Wheel produced with the families of those assisted with intellectual disabilities in follow-up at APAE-Niterói.

The family as an agency of socialization, protection and participation.

The family is the main agent of primary socialization and where care relationships are produced between its members through protection, reception, respect for individuality and empowerment of the other. In each family, there are values transmitted from generation to generation, involving affection and identity.

The family to which the disabled person belongs

plays an important role in opposing their marginalization. It has the important function of providing to make the desiring subject, a person who can transform their impulses into desires, seeking to fulfill them within the framework of their difference and through it.

The response that the family will give to this challenge will depend on past experiences, economic situation, as well as ethnic background and family relationships, among other influences, which, in turn, will determine whether the challenge of creating, caring for and educating their child will be faced. The family may have difficulties in fulfilling its social role of educating individuals to actively participate in today's society that emphasizes aspects such as efficiency and effectiveness.

Social work with Families finds its ethical and political foundations in the Federal Constitution of 1988; in the Organic Law of Social Assistance, of 1993; in the National Policy for Social Assistance, 2004; reaffirming the adoption of the centrality of the family as a structuring element of the offers of social assistance and respecting the different forms of organization of families.

The actions of this work involve the recognition of the organization of the family's daily life, the exercise of roles and functions in the family, the relationships with the disability, the relationships of authority and affection; the values, representations and practices of care and socialization of its members and also the coexistence.

Families develop their own mechanisms to face the challenges in caring for the person with a disability, these mechanisms vary according to culturally installed beliefs and with offers and availability of resources. Faced with this new situation, it is very likely that there will be a shock, a disbelief; Families can become tense, disorganized, conflicted, and even break up with the separation of the parents, or even the "forgetfulness" of the other child.

Therefore, it is necessary to adopt a clear methodological approach, which promotes a critical reflection on the situations experienced by families that have a person with a disability at their core, and favors the perception of dimensions and minimizes the consequences of ableism.

We seek methodological approaches that can meet the demands through spaces that promote technical intervention actions to help families.

METHODOLOGY

Conversation circle approach with families

Conversation circles are collective spaces used for discussion and reflection on various topics, and can be used for different purposes, including action planning. Where families report their experiences. Based on the conversation circle methodology, the context for planning technical actions that can help these families is developed.

The themes are previously defined together with a psychologist who accompanies the conversation circle, begins with the presentation of the participants, the topic to be addressed and a reflection message lasts for approximately 40 minutes being held fortnightly. During the conversation, the technical team makes observations regarding the participants' reports where all the information is analyzed and directed.

Conversation solidifies a practice in which social representations are respected in a conflictive, cooperative and consensus-building environment, minimizing resistance to listening, reflecting and analyzing the problems presented by families. In the different relationships of everyday life, the peculiar aspects of each place are characterized in its historical, political and cultural context that will facilitate the apprehension of new ways of thinking, acting, doing and promoting knowledge through words, gestures and acts.

CASE STUDY - CONVERSATION WHEEL

Theme: who takes care of who cares?

Theme presented in partnership with APAE - Niterói and Anhanguera College in the conversation circle for the families of those assisted by the APAE institution, the psychology students of the college accompanied by the course coordinator and the teacher along with the team that monitors the families of those assisted by the institution social worker and psychologist.

After presenting the theme, a report caught the attention of the group that was participating, a mother reports her story that after receiving the information that her son had Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) after a period of almost two years in search of a diagnosis, went through a grieving process, because the initial idea she had of pregnancy would be a “normal” baby like most other mothers, she needed to rediscover the joy of being a mother and how to love that child with the same love that a mother receives. your child in your arms being a special child on the autism spectrum, the period of acceptance was very difficult. She decided to give up her teaching profession to dedicate herself fully to monitoring her son so that he could have access to all possible treatments aiming at a better quality of life in the expectation that at some point she could resume her routine including her work, according to this mother’s report, she was unable to resume her professional life, the process is very difficult, little help from the family, difficult access to support networks, the waiting time is very long and there is little access to information. She lives alone with her son, she reports that in many moments she feels tired, she does not see herself as a warrior, as she often hears this speech from people, but says that she did not choose to live this life experience, she came to her and learned to deal with and accept it. and that doesn’t change her joy in being a mother. Today her biggest dream is to see her son happy and included in society without prejudice, just being different.

In this report it was possible to identify many social and emotional difficulties in the family structure, there is the financial issue due to the mother not having the structural conditions to work, depending on the social benefits that often take time to be accessed, a woman who cancels herself in social life and professional to dedicate exclusively to the child without the help of the father, an intense routine of comings and goings in search of treatments for the child, not allowing them to have a social life such as leisure, culture etc..., the difficulties of accessing information, doctors, medication when necessary, sport, therapeutic accompaniments and inclusive school for the social and cognitive development of this child.

This report was only possible because this mother could have a space to talk about her experience, feeling confident that there would be no kind of

prejudice, criticism or judgment.

The team that accompanied the conversation circle can provide guidance when necessary to the mother for access to care networks, providing psychological support at no cost to the mother by the faculty psychology team and strengthening the bond of this mother with the institution so that she has support for the continuity of monitoring the child at the institution and support of the team in care for the family at the institution such as family reception, lectures, social and technical meetings. The institution APAE-Niterói holds fortnightly conversation circles coordinated by the social worker and psychologist who serve the families.

Conversation circles allow families to have a voice in this space, feeling part of the group, choices and decisions. Also an opportunity to work on listening to others, respecting different opinions.

According to Geraldi “[...] the stories that make us unique and ‘go repeatable’. Uncertain uniqueness, because if I understand with words that, before being mine, were and are also someone else’s, I will never be sure if I am speaking or if something speaks for me [...]”. (GERALDI, 2005, p. 22).

Within family relationships, ableism can also occur, which often manifests itself implicitly, when family members in a protectionist way consider people with disabilities as incapable subjects, developing speeches and actions that harm and frustrate the development of their autonomy and disrespect their desires and emotions, often taking away the right to answer about their own desires and desires, without a voice and no time to resolve certain situations in their life. It is in this context that the Institution APAE Niterói identified the importance of discussing the place of speech in demystifying the existence of a universal subject, who believes that all people start from a common position of access to speech and listening (MONBAÇA, 2017). The aim is to resume the role of the family, redirecting care, providing tools for the family to build new plans, or adjust old dreams to suit the new script of life, for her and consequently for her children.

Understanding ableism as prejudice against people with disabilities, as they define subjects and bodies from a standardized reference as a “normal” body,

one of the forms of this oppression reveals itself in society through attitudinal barriers. These are defined, according to current legislation, as any obstacle, obstacle, attitude or behavior that limits or prevents the person's social participation, as well as the enjoyment, fruition and exercise of their rights to accessibility, freedom of movement and expression, communication, access to information, understanding, safe circulation, among others.

In this sense, attitudinal barriers are established in the social field, where human relationships focus on the limitations of individuals and not on their potential, attitudes or behaviors that prevent or impair the social participation of people with disabilities in equal conditions and opportunities with others. the other subjects.

Amaral (1988) explains attitudinal barrier as a defense interspersed between two people, where one is in a certain more favorable position in relation to the other.

CONCLUSION

When spaces for exchanges are created between parents and between them and administrators and professionals, we are increasing sociability and the ability of these groups to participate in the institution itself, thus expanding everyone's commitment to the full development of the patient, in their particularities. and favoring social inclusion and neutralizing enabling actions.

The Conversation Wheel Project defines its mission, goals and objectives based on the service to welcome families. Thus, by articulating with the institution's professionals, prevention actions, guidance and establishment of support groups for parents, the aim is to improve the quality of life of these families.

In conversation circles, when we use a different perspective to analyze the actions of families, we are able to envision possible paths in the direction of making the meeting attractive and the family as the protagonist. In this way, we can say that the development of a good practice is done in listening and looking, articulated with significant learning, which add greater meaning and significance to the family as a subject.

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